

APPLICATION OF INK WITH PUFF EFFECT FOR IMPROVEMENT OF ERGONOMIC PROPERTIES OF PACKAGING

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Abstract: *Ergonomic packaging should provide the handling of a product efficiently, effectively, and intuitively, ensuring ease of access to the product and safe grip of the packaging, thus improving user experience. Consumers should be enabled to comfortably lift, hold, and open packaging. This can be achieved by an appropriate size, shape, and material of the packaging. The aim of this paper was to investigate the possibility of using screen-printing and ink with added puff base to enhance the ergonomic properties of the packaging. The added puff base gives the print a three-dimensional shape and surface properties associated with greater surface roughness, also it enhances tactile perception and provides a more secure grip. This preliminary study was conducted by objective and subjective evaluation methods. The experiment was conducted to characterize the effect of differences in tactile properties of the specimen's contact surface on the force achieved by manually pulling. The specimens were printed on three different substrates using a manual screen printing technique. In addition to the substrate, the amount of added puff substance in ink (0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%) was also varied. The total number of different printed samples was 12. Results indicate that the specimens with a rough surface result in better grip and higher manual pulling force.*

Keywords: packaging, ergonomics, puff base

1 INTRODUCTION

Tactile perception and interaction with objects play a key role in our daily lives. The sensitivity of the skin of the palm gives us a sense of touch, which provides us with feedback about the outside world and allows us to interact with the products we use (Striano and Bushnell, 2005). Touch is one of the most basic ways of communicating with the environment, which enables us to handle objects and evaluate their tactile properties (Darden and Schwartz, 2015).

Haptic perception refers to the perception of tactile properties of materials and surfaces. Although consumers use a wide range of vocabulary to describe the haptic impression of materials and surfaces (Meyer, 2001; Kawazu et al, 2000), Hollins identified two robust dimensions of haptic perception - hardness: hard-soft and roughness: smooth/rough (Hollins, 1994). In this context, friction between human skin and object surfaces plays a key role. Friction allows us to safely handle objects (Veijgen, Masen and Van Der Heide, 2012; Veijgen, Van Der Heide and Masen, 2010; Derler and Gerhardt, 2012). Although research has been done dealing with tactile perception and friction between skin and materials, little is known about the perception of slipperiness and its effect on grip safety (Bergmann Tiest, 2010). Some research has focused on grip and sliding when lifting objects, analyzing the effect of object shape and surface materials on grip (Kinoshita et al, 1997; Jenmalm, Goodwin and Johansson, 1998). However, these studies did not deal with the improvement of materials and surfaces, nor did they take psychophysical factors into account. Studies on the measurement of friction between skin and materials show the complexity of the overlapping parameters. Further research is needed to better understand the perceived quality of achieving a firm grip (Derler et al, 2009; Bergmann Tiest, 2010).

Screen printing with added puff base in the ink is a technique that gives a three-dimensional effect and texture to prints (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Screen printing with puff effect (613originals, 2023).

It involves using a special printing ink or paste that contains an additive called a "puff base". When the print is exposed to heat during the drying process, the puff base expands, creating a raised or puffed appearance on the surface of the print. By incorporating a puff base, the print exhibits altered surface characteristics that can be visually and tactile perceived.

The subject of this paper is the investigation of the tactile characteristics of prints created using the manual screen printing technique with the addition of a puff base. One notable outcome achieved through the inclusion of the puff base in the printing ink is an increase in roughness. The study aims to explore the potential use of such prints in enhancing the ergonomic properties of products designed for manual use, such as packaging. In the context of manual product manipulation, roughness plays a significant role. Higher levels of roughness provide a more secure grip, facilitating the handling and manipulation of the product.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The objective of the experimental part of the research is to test the hypothesis through laboratory work. The proposed hypothesis is that prints printed by manual screen printing technique with the addition of a puff base in ink could be used to improve the ergonomic characteristics of packaging. This paper examines the impact of incorporating a puff base in printing on both comfort and manual pulling forces. The research was carried out through an experiment followed by a survey. Given that printing with the addition of puff base in different percentages produces prints with different characteristics, e.g. roughness changes, the experiment investigated the maximum hand-pulling forces of an object coated with printed samples, with the assumption that the tactile properties of the printed sample will affect the feeling of comfort and manual pulling forces. Prints were printed on different paper materials and different amounts of added puff base (0%, 10%, 20%, or 30%). 14 participants completed the survey and experiment, 7 male and 7 female. All participants were between 25 and 35 years old. The ambient temperature of the room was $23 \pm 2^\circ$, and the relative humidity was $50 \pm 2\%$. Seo et al (2008) were engaged in similar research, based on which the methodology of this research was defined.

2.1 Test samples

The test samples were printed by the manual screen printing technique on a carousel machine manufactured by Centropapir, model no.S.6S4T.B. All prints were printed in black using water-based Teflex ink. Teflex manufacturer's puff base was added to the ink in three different percentages of 10%, 20%, and 30%.

The screen printing mesh count of 120 l/cm was used. After printing, the prints were dried at 133°. The prints were made on different paper substrates, including bulky paper (164-180 g/m²), matte-coated kunstdruk paper (257-300 g/m²), and paperboard (250 g/m²). The print had a rectangular shape in size of 135 x 30 mm and 100% coverage. Given the variations mentioned, 12 different types of prints were obtained (Table 1). It is noteworthy to mention that additional tactile characteristic of these exact prints on textile materials were evaluated and discussed in a previous study (Bošnjaković et al, 2022).

Table 1. Categorization of printed samples.

Print type specimen name	Substrate	The added amount of puff base in the ink
1-0	<i>bulky paper (164-180 g/m²)</i>	0 %
1-10	<i>bulky paper (164-180 g/m²)</i>	10 %
1-20	<i>bulky paper (164-180 g/m²)</i>	20 %
1-30	<i>bulky paper (164-180 g/m²)</i>	30 %
2-0	<i>paperboard (250 g/m²)</i>	0 %
2-10	<i>paperboard (250 g/m²)</i>	10 %
2-20	<i>paperboard (250 g/m²)</i>	20 %
2-30	<i>paperboard (250 g/m²)</i>	30 %
3-0	<i>matte-coated kunstdruk paper (257-300 g/m²)</i>	0 %
3-10	<i>matte-coated kunstdruk paper (257-300 g/m²)</i>	10 %
3-20	<i>matte-coated kunstdruk paper (257-300 g/m²)</i>	20 %
3-30	<i>matte-coated kunstdruk paper (257-300 g/m²)</i>	30%

2. 2 Experimental apparatus, survey, and procedure

Participants entered the measurement room individually and received instructions. They were given the freedom to adjust their position in front of the experimental apparatus based on their dominant hand (Rowson and Yoxall, 2011; Peebles and Norris, 2003). The experimental setup (Figure 2) incorporated a Shimadzu Compact Tabletop Testing EZ-LX machine, equipped with a 2.5 kN measuring cell and a testing speed of 1 mm/min. The TrapeziumX software was utilized to record the maximum manual pulling force values during the tests in newtons (N). To accurately measure the manual pulling force exerted on the samples, instead of using conventional clamping tools the tool coated with printed samples was used. The height of the tool was customized to accommodate the individual's height, ensuring optimal comfort during the experiment. Specifically, the participants were instructed to use their fingertips, with their thumb being placed on one side of the coated tool while the other fingers secured the sample on the opposite side (both sides were coated with the same printed sample). Their task was to pull the coated tool with the maximum force possible in a downward direction. As soon as the participant

sensed the slip of the sample through their fingers, they immediately stopped pulling which concluded the measurement.

Figure 2. a) Experimental apparatus b) Participant testing the samples.

Subsequently, participants were presented with a survey. The survey consisted of 12 sections, corresponding to the number of tested samples. Within each section, participants were asked to assign a grade to predefined characteristics on a scale ranging from 1 to 10. A rating of 1 represented the lowest grade, while a rating of 10 represented the highest. Participants were asked to evaluate the pleasantness to the touch and the ease of manual pulling. To give subjective estimates through tactile perception, participants gently ran their fingertips across the surface of each sample, drawing upon established methodologies (Wongsriruksa et al, 2012; Bergmann Tiest, 2010; Srinivasan, Whitehouse and LaMotte, 1990; Hollins et al, 2000; Chen and Ge, 2017). This survey not only made it easier to gather subjective ratings but also provided participants with a short break to rest their hands, muscles, and nerves. The same organized method was used for each sample until all different variations were tested.

3 RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the results of the conducted survey on tactile evaluations of printed samples. Everyone had the task of evaluating samples based on two criteria: pleasantness to the touch and ease of manual pulling, which reflects stability and grip security (1 - lowest grade, 10 - highest grade). Samples 3-10, 3-20, and 3-30, printed on matte-coated kunstdruk paper, received the highest estimates in terms of pleasantness to the touch. Additionally, it was observed that samples 1-10 and 2-10, when compared to other samples printed on the

Figure 3. Graphic representation of the results of subjective estimates of printed samples by 14 participants.

same material, were rated more favorably due to their lower value of added puff base (10%) in terms of touch pleasantness. Additionally, it was observed that samples 1-10 and 2-10, when compared to other samples printed on the same material, were rated more favorably due to their lower value of added puff base (10%) in terms of touch pleasantness. Regarding the subjective estimates of ease of manual pulling, it is important to note that these ratings were generally lower compared to the ratings for pleasantness to the touch. The highest ratings were obtained for samples printed on matte-coated kunstdruk paper sample 3-20, followed by 1-10. It is noted that regarding both evaluated criteria, namely pleasantness to the touch and ease of manual pulling, the samples with a small amount (10%) of added puff base received better subjective estimates compared to the print samples without it. The normal distribution function was utilized to calculate the normal distribution based on the specified mean values of manual pulling forces and standard deviation (Figure 4). The mean values of manual pulling forces and standard deviations are given in Table 2.

Figure 4. The normal distribution function for every printed sample.

Table 2. Mean values of manual pulling forces and standard deviations.

Specimen	Mean values of manual pulling forces [N]	Standard deviation	N
1-0	69.17	29.08	14
1-10	76.32	26.51	14
1-20	75.27	29.69	14
1-30	71.32	29.82	14
2-0	62.86	26.32	14
2-10	75.70	30.30	14
2-20	78.18	33.26	14
2-30	71.99	28.98	14
3-0	67.99	29.31	14
3-10	77.54	31.61	14
3-20	78.37	33.50	14
3-30	75.25	29.82	14

Figure 4 displays the two most significant curves: one representing the manual pulling forces of the sample observed with the highest forces achieved, along with the highest standard deviation (depicted by green rhombus signs- sample 3-20), and another curve representing the printed sample observed with the lowest forces achieved along with the lowest standard deviation (depicted by red triangle signs- sample 2-0). The absence of significant deviations from normality is reflected in the standard deviations. Notably, the curve for the 3-20 sample clearly shows a rightward shift of the normal distribution, indicating favorable characteristics for manual pulling forces.

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to assess the effect of the printed sample on forces achieved by manual pulling. Mauchly's test of sphericity, which examines the assumption that the variances of the differences between all possible pairs of within-subject conditions are equal, was evaluated. Due to a violation of the sphericity assumption, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied. The main effect of the printed sample was found to be statistically significant, $F(4.745, 61.691)=3.582, p<0.05$, indicating a significant difference in forces achieved by manually pulling across the levels of printed samples. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Bonferroni correction revealed significant differences between specific levels of printed samples. Specimen 2-0 demonstrated significantly lower forces achieved by manual pulling compared to 1-10, 1-20, 2-10, 2-20, 3-10, 3-20, and 3-30. This result indicates that maximum manual pulling forces were significantly higher for samples with added puff base compared to those without it.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Ergonomic packaging aims to provide efficient, effective, and intuitive handling of a product, ensuring a secure grip for improved user experience. In this research, the aim was to investigate the potential of utilizing screen-printing and ink with an added puff base to further enhance the secure grip properties of packaging. The puff base introduces new visual and tactile effects, transforming the print into a three-dimensional one with altered surface characteristics. Notably, the addition of a puff base enhances the roughness of the printed surface, which is crucial for secure grip and effective manipulation of packaging. The research methodology involved an experimental setup followed by a survey to evaluate the maximum forces of manual pulling of printed samples. The prints were applied to various paper materials, with varying percentages of puff base added (0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%). A total of 12 different printed samples were generated. It was found that samples with added puff base exhibited significantly higher subjective estimates regarding pleasantness to the touch and ease of pulling. In accordance with that, recorded pulling forces were also higher in the case of printed samples with added puff base in the ink compared to samples without it. This effect can be attributed to multiple factors. Firstly, the addition of a puff base increased the roughness of the print surface, providing a more tactile and textured grip, which in turn facilitated a firmer hold and increased friction during manual pulling. Secondly, the altered tactile properties, such as increased softness and texture and the three-dimensional effect contributed to an improved perception of grip, thereby leading to higher manual pulling forces. Also, psychological factors related to the visual perception of depth and texture created by the presence of the puff base may have influenced participants to perceive an enhanced grip and subsequently provide higher forces during manual pulling. These findings suggest the potential of incorporating a screen printing technique with added puff base in the ink to enhance grip characteristics and manual manipulation of packaging products.

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